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SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS WITH REGARD TO TYPE OF SCHOOL

Education

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of the study is to find out the significant difference in social intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school. The investigator used the survey method of research. The investigator has randomly selected 300 higher secondary students in Sivagiri educational district for the present study. Totally ten schools were taken for the study. The sampling technique used in the study is random sampling method. The investigator used a standardized social intelligence scale for the present study. The scale was prepared and standardized by National Psychological Corporation, Agra. The investigator used one way ANOVA and Scheffe test for analyze the data. From the results of F-test, the investigator found that there is significant difference in social intelligence of higher secondary school students with respect to type of school.

KEYWORDS:

Social Intelligence, type of school, ANOVA, Scheffe

INTRODUCTION

Social intelligence (SI) is the ability to get along well others, and to get them to cooperative with you. Sometimes referred to simplistically as "people skills" SI includes an awareness of situations and the social dynamics that govern them and knowledge of interaction styles and strategies that can help a person achieve his or her objectives in dealing with others. It also involves a certain amount of self-insight and a consciousness of one's own perceptions and reaction patterns. According to Edward L. Thorndike, Social intelligence as the ability to understand others and act wisely in human relations. Human relations as commonly visualized are day to day dealing with other people at house and at work. The success or failure of a task depends on our handling the situation and the people involved with the situation. Social intelligence as the ability to understand people in life and to make one's headway through them by dealing with them or handling them. Political leaders in society, for example, could be said to possess higher social intelligence, though they may have failed in school. Social intelligence is the part of dimidiates mental ability which generates in him the capacity to adept himself to society. This ability enables the individuals to form relations in the society because man is a gregarious, social animal and such relations are essential for his existence. This kind of intelligence comprehends the field of skills in behaviour. Along with skill in behaviour are implicit the qualities of personality and characters, independency, mood honesty deviousness, honour, nature, these indicate the individual's social intelligence. Many people find themselves failure in life because the doubt of possesses this social intelligence. In general, abstract social intelligence keep pace with each other and function together leaders exploit this form of intelligence to win popularity in public life. Measuring SI involves identifying interaction skills and then assessing them behaviourally. All human interaction takes place with some context or other, and effectiveness involves mastering the contexts within which one is called upon to interact. So according to this reasoning, SI means understanding contexts, knowing how to navigate within and between various contexts, and knowing how to behave in various contexts so as achieve one's objectives. In other words, SI is inferred from behaviour, so we use various observable behaviour as indicators of SI.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

In the present era, which is marked with social confrontations due to diminishing social norms, it is difficult to lead a successful life in a society without social intelligence. An individual's social intelligence can be known or measured only from his adjustability. To be well adjusted, an individual has to be intelligent so that he can think rationally, act purposefully and deal effectively with the environment. A person is socially intelligent and adjustable only when he moulds himself according to the needs of the society. While living in society, man should live with love, cooperation and kindness. It is because every society has certain customs, traditions, norms and ideals, the fulfillment of which is the primary responsibility of man, so that he can reside well in the society. Thorndike (1920) has given three forms of

intelligence as, abstract intelligence (pertaining) to understanding & managing ideas), mechanical intelligence (dealing with concrete objects) and social intelligence (engaging with people). Social intelligence is the capacity of a man to understand the feelings and emotions of other and react according to the circumstances. It enable them to express their viewpoints strongly and make others upon it. It has two key constituents that are recognized as distinctly personal and social immature one is intrapersonal intelligence that pertains to the person's ability to again access to his or her own internal, emotional life and other is interpersonal intelligence which includes an individual's ability. To notice and make distinctions among other individuals. The higher secondary students being in the adolescent period generally are aggressive, frustrated, disobedient, irritated, notorious, and are unable to manage social relationships. As a result they get involved in the cases of theft, bullying, ragging, rapes and even murder. The causes can be many including their ill treatment in the classroom mal administration of educational institutions, unhealthy environment at home and school, etc. The need of the hour demands that they have to be educated about social norms and traditions so that they are in a better position to manage social relationships. They have to be trained in acquiring social intelligence skills which are the basic of adjustment. Social intelligence is the ability of an individual to understand and deal with person it proves successful in personal as well as social actions. With this background, the investigator wants to study the social intelligence of higher secondary students with regard to type of school.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

There is no significant difference in social intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school.

RESEARCH METHOD USED

The investigator used the survey method of research.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The population for present study was higher secondary students in Sivagiri Educational District.

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

The investigator has randomly selected 300 higher secondary students in Sivagiri educational district for the present study. Totally ten schools were taken for the study. The sampling technique used in the study is random sampling method.

TOOL USED

The investigator used a standardized social intelligence scale for the present study. The scale was prepared and standardized by National Psychological Corporation, Agra.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE USED

The investigator used one way ANOVA and Scheffe test for analyze the data.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

H₀ : There is no significant difference in social intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school.

Table-1
One way ANOVA showing significant difference in social intelligence of higher secondary students with regard to type of school

Variable	Sources of variation	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean square	Calculated 'F' value	Remark
Social intelligence	Between Groups	5053.855	2	2526.927	34.367	S
	Within groups	21837.675	297	73.528		

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 'F' value (34.367) is greater than the table value (3.03) for df (2,297) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence then null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is significant difference in Social intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school.

Table-2
The Scheffe test showing the significant difference in social intelligence of higher secondary students with respect to type of school

Government	Government Aided	Private	Result
46.07	54.34	-	*
46.07	-	55.21	*
-	54.34	55.21	

*Significant difference at 5% level of significance

It is inferred from the above table that there is significant difference between government and government aided higher secondary students and also there is significant difference between government and private higher secondary students in their social intelligence.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

From the results of F-test, the investigator found that there is significant difference in social intelligence of higher secondary school students with respect to type of school. The government aided higher secondary students have better social intelligence than the government higher secondary students. The private school higher secondary students have better social intelligence than the government school higher secondary students. The reason may be that in government aided and private higher secondary students the teachers may be effectively motivated the students to take part in the extra and co-curricular activities. Students with strong social intelligence participate more in the classroom, have more positive attitudes about and involvement with school, are more accepted by classmates, and are given more instruction and positive feedback by teachers.

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